

- [MIMS 2.801 - MESS0037: the Eight Domain Array - badge and meaning](#)
- [MESS0042: Operator Skillset Inventory](#)
- [MESS0048: Operator Skillset Inventory; C Team & the Future Soldier](#)
- “Speed, Surprise, and Violence of Action.”
- “Slow is smooth, smooth is fast.”

MESS 0049

MIMS 2.8.60.1 - SSIVA-PADEP¹

Above: Speed, Surprise, *Intense* Violence of Action

Below: Preparation, Actionability, Devastation, Experience, Potency

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¹ Figure 1 - Image of Kirlian Photographs of hand; credit: InnerEnergy/author [Kirlian Photography Camera Equipment](#)

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ABSTRACT

The current paradigms of special operations, CQB, CQC, and general clearing tactics are somewhat in flux. The reason is that the War on Terror revealed many flaws in “present” (former) tactics, and now leaked footage of Delta Force operations, combined with visioneering and general re-visioning of the “future soldier” (see MESS0048) means that the true potential of the operator is not yet really known.

In that paper, the discussion tended towards issues related to discussions of gender, skills, and how objective measures are; finally towards tournaments of specops teams and the creation of the Next Future Soldier. In this paper, we wish to discuss the augmentation of the ‘wisdom’ mentioned at the top of page 1. There is nothing “wrong” about these principles; however though simplicity is divine, there is in fact missing information that is martially important. Long term, the goal is to create operator equivalents (with real inventories) to the fiction set, well over 600 points, or even 700 - for each operator.

The new paradigm shown in the delta force training videos is not about being slow, or just simple violence. It **fully** demonstrates the SSIVA PADEP concept: there is a surprise element coming from high speed, and then intensity to that violence of action. Beneath that is the truth revealed: Preparation, Actionability, Devastation, Experience, and Potency. The potency and devastation ‘bars’ are very high, and there is incredible actionability in the planning for the mission. But most important is preparation; the planning phase is very important, and all of the training that went into the operator in producing capabilities creates the potential energy for the release of the SSIVA concept.

Introduction

The author is well acquainted with violence². His first boxing ‘incident’ was to have his ass kicked, at age three (3) years of age, on the north side of town off Russell Cave Rd. His multiple black belts, training by a US marine and captain (at a prison) in jiu jitsu stlye Judo, as well as boxing, and intense studies of action and the world’s provision of self defense case studies, are but a part of his knowledge. He also devised the NAILStm women’s self-defense program³, the “49 Shaping Hands,”⁴ and “Springing Style” boxing, which combines the top styles of peekaboo, philly shell, stone box, herky-jerky, teleport footwork (from gongfu), and the “52 blocks”⁵. His specialty is [REDACTED] knife [REDACTED].

Nevertheless, the author is **not** an operator.⁶ He merely absorbs as much of their philosophies, via multiple arenas and methods, as possible. As a visioneer⁷, he would like to contribute to the evolution of operations, in the smallest of ways, with respect to these veterans⁸. Furthermore, he dedicates this paper to that one Navy SEAL he **failed** to bring peace in 2012 - to reconnect to the Source and “feel” again after the

² MESS0010: MIMS 2.81 - Violence as a MIMS

³ NAILS

⁴ 49 Empty Hand Techniques.pdf

⁵ 52 Blocks Explained | Self Defense | FightFast

⁶ Ex Civilian DOD/engineering

⁷ The Once and Future American

⁸ His brother is an active duty US Marine, “oorah”

sacrifices in the War on Terror from 2003-2012 - and hopes all the teams find that peace the warrior deserves **and has earned** for defending their home, country, family, community, and freedom.

With that said, the author believes that not only is violence an important topic, for reality and for safety and security; he believes it is absolutely 100% vital to understand its mims = anti-mims axis (MAMA) of violence (particularly as it affects safety, security, and stability (SSS).) Note that freedom is not something we claim to have *in* that consideration, for freedoms end when (without just cause), one infringes upon the rights of another with *actual* violence. Words are not violence. Threats are illegal, but not violence.

Intensity of (or Intense) Violence of Action

There's only a small distinction between the two ideas. The first is a description of power level, and the second is an adjective to describe the Volume of the Violence.

The common person is actually familiar with this. Grabbing a shirt in public is assault, but it isn't a punch. And a punch to the eye, especially between boys, is not considered anywhere near the violence of a gangland shooting. And a drive- by shooting, as intense as it is, is nothing compared to a firefight in Fallujah. And that is little compared to the close quarters combat of trench or jungle warfare. And this is little compared to a dive-bomber at Midway. Etc. There is a continual increase, and thus far the greatest violence witnessed on Earth was the "Arrow of Brahma"⁹ which vaporized multiple cities in the Harappan India, or the Sodom and Gomorrah story¹⁰. Second would be Hiroshima, etc. These forms of violence actually make the Cat 4 scale of cataclysms¹¹. Regionally, they are quite disastrous.

In this same way, we can also understand the clear relationship between the D and I; the "middle finger" of both hands. Devastation is directly proportional to Intensity. Does this relationship hold throughout?

- ❖ Speed Preparation - The better the preparation, the faster you can go "smoothly"
- ❖ Surprise Actionability - To have "action ability" is good; but with surprise, chances go up.
- ❖ Intensity Devastation - Raising the adversary's devastation bar is a matter of intensity.
- ❖ Violence Experience - The inexperienced send violence in haphazard directions.
- ❖ Action Potency - It is important before taking action to be potent; potent action is more compassionate to the adversary; it is far worse to hamstring conflict than to end it fast and with devastation so complete that all ire ceases. Bear in mind, there are no 'winners' in a war.

There are many things to be said about each item; but let's not be pedantic or condescending. Brevity is the soul of wit, when it comes to pragmatic subjects like violence. In short: the top operators and teams already intuitively know the above. So it remains to us to belabor only specific points. Take, for example, Experience.

The average age of active SEAL teams is 35 years old¹². Same for Delta Force. Green Berets is 31; Rangers is 25 but MARSOC/Raiders is probably 26 or 27yo¹³. So this explains the general motion from "lower" teams towards DEVGRU or SOFD-1 in career paths. It is a simple matter of experience, which is expensive¹⁴ and therefore valuable for the wisdom it brings. In the inventory made (for fictional operators), XP is related to

⁹ [Shang Di, Heaven, and Dao](#)

¹⁰ Genesis 19

¹¹ [Birkeland Polyphase Superweb Appendix](#)

¹² [Navy Seal Demographics and Statistics In The US](#)

¹³ [Q&A with MARSOC battalion commander - The San Diego Union-Tribune](#)

¹⁴ [Training special operators is expensive. Why does it cost so much to train a Navy SEAL? - Quora](#)

the age of the property and the score; but we won't pit the programs against one another. SEALs/UDT and Raiders are more historic than Delta Force, but there is no doubt that (save perhaps the CIA tier 1 or SAS) the deltas are top of the food chain.¹⁵

Regarding Potency

Potency is a matter of not merely strength, and not merely power¹⁶ applied. It is actually a matter of penetrative ability. There is a secret to it:

- a) piercing the adversary's guard/defense with
- b) Efficiency and
- c) Effortlessness (in terms of drain to source) or even Ruthlessness
- d) Least expenditure possible

By being potent, rather than impotent, the operator (or purveyor of damage and violence) can have a rapid effect upon the MAMA. But it isn't actually a linear scale. For example you might over apply SSIVA and yield a highly anti-mimsical result. The United States ran out of atomic bombs¹⁷. But it did stop at two¹⁸. If this, or the carpet bombing of Germany had continued, the entire world would have been at risk to a rage-drunk with power. Therefore the secret to potency yielding mimsical results is (as one should expect) always restraint where possible. A blind sword is a danger to the holder and wielder. But a sheathed sword has **potential**, and this, like voltage, creates the proper tension for results in FLEXION.

- Flexibility - the ability to bend around obstacles and achieve key objectives is 100% necessary to the operator's success.
- Tension - not only in potential, but the actual application of a field that displaces the adversarial position.
 - The better the PADEP, the better the displacement with, as said above, effortlessness
- The key to the combination of the two, is Experience.

Regarding Action and Actionability, this is related to experience, but also the provision of Surprise and of course, the expedient, and disciplined control of Violence. Again, widespread violence is low on the MAMA (figure 2 below; credit: author), while also reduced in potency (generally speaking). Think of a gangstAr's widespread spray of a fully automatic 9mm Uzi into a porch. If it hits anyone, seems invariably it is a child. Absolutely despicable and irresponsible use of violence and weapons!! Unacceptable.

Figure 2 - MAMA axial diagram; TCM s Traditional Chinese Medicine; credit: author

¹⁵ This was *not* clear to the author even last year, as he continued to read through all of the Tom Clancy material, study the web, and tlak with his marine brother. Such si the marketing surrounding the issue that SEAL Team-6 and Green Berets get top billing. But as Matrix (Delta Force) says in "Commando": "I eat Green Berets for BREAKFAST!"

¹⁶ [MESS0024: MIMS 2.21 - Engineering MIMS Philosophy into a Plug and Play Platform \(P7 Resolution\)](#)

¹⁷ [Did the U.S. plan to drop more than two atomic bombs on Japan?](#)

¹⁸ [Did the United States have a third atomic bomb to drop on Japan? | Wyzant Ask An Expert](#)

Becoming PADEP't

Operators, now and in the future, will continuously work on PADEP. Being able to adapt, adopt, overcome is key to being adept; and therefore Preparation (in the form of training, and not merely planning) will always reign (hence: the thumb). Actionability requires confidence, direction, and a positive attitude (hence: the first, pointing finger). Devastation leads to heart damage, and also is a matter of “Screw you” attitude (hence: the middle finger/PC channel). Therefore the devastation bar on the adversary should be raised quickly, and with the least amount of damage to the self as possible - to the operator’s heart.

As for Experience, this should be viewed in terms mostly of wisdom, but also “real world” value (aka “in the shit”), meaning that there is a grasp of full reality. This relates to the fourth finger in a couple of subtle, but unimportant ways. And finally Potency, the ‘little thing’ that makes all the difference in the end, results in either success or failure. As a “P” it can swap with Preparation, so that all the little things that count are controlled, and Potency itself becomes the controller. This model, therefore is wrap-around; and more importantly, in axial connection to the other side. Just as it is in your cortex.

Number One Rule of Thumb

Preparation - being able to capture opportunities

The “double entendre” of E is Execution. “Sha”¹⁹ in Chinese refers not only to the actual swinging of the axe but the capability, and then *follow-through* to actually do so. Not to resort back to fiction, all the time, but it illustrates the point very well:

In the show “24” Jack Bauer distinguishes himself²⁰ by having several features. Yes he is willing to go further than anyone else, do anything, to whomever he needs to, to save lives. But more importantly he knows how far things *have to go* to succeed, and is willing to go there, for the mission, even if it hurts his soul. That’s his Delta training²¹. In his own words, and never more true words have been said by a fictional operator,

“Jack Bauer: When I am activated, when I am brought into a situation, there is a reason. And that reason is to complete the objectives of my mission at all costs.

Blaine Mayer: ...Even if it means breaking the law.

Jack Bauer: For a combat soldier, the difference between success and failure is your ability to adapt to your enemy. The people that I deal with, they don't care about your rules. All they care about is a result. My job is to stop them from completing their objective, at all costs. I simply adapted. In answer to your question, 'Am I above the law?', no sir. I am more than willing to be judged by the people you claim to represent. I will let them decide what price I should pay. But please sir, do not sit there with that smug look on your face and expect me to regret the decisions I have made. Because, sir, the truth is... I don't.”

¹⁹ 杀 shā - to kill, murder, fight, weaken or reduce, to smart (dialect), to counteract

²⁰ (especially in the early and last 2 seasons, although the writers betrayed the hero in the end of each day 8 and day 9!)

²¹ [Jack Bauer before Day 1 | Wiki 24 | Fandom](#)

It's worth pointing out that Senator Mayer died later that day, trying to force Jack to do it "the right way" as the bad guys, again and to Jack's point, don't care about our rules. POS²² operate off of a completely other set of unethical considerations. Terrorists, criminals, miscreants, politicians, NGO governments, and secret societies operate in unethical borders, based upon Shi (positional advantage) alone²³. All there is is power²⁴, influence, access, and affluence²⁵. They also only understand others that know this. Operators are people who, for the most part, are "sheep dogs" that protect the sheep from these wolves, because they choose to "do good" by doing difficult mission sets that regular Joes cannot do, without the training, capability, or stomach.

More importantly, back to Jack Bauer: he also routinely accomplishes the "impossible" by going where others cannot go, and others frequently let him down, betray him, and fail to do the right thing (even Presidents). As was said above, even the authors betrayed him. Think of the meaning of the self-sacrifice now. It isn't only the life on the line. It's your soul's belief in greater hopes. As the saying goes about KIA/POWs, "All gave some, some gave all."

There isn't an operator alive today (unless he is an egomaniac author) that wouldn't give up all his awards and honors, rank even, to have back his brothers (and some sisters) in arms, whom they consider the real heroes!

Preparation, and repetition of training and planning and practice of execution, leads to the ability to actually achieve what you say you will.

Thinking of real world scenarios, there are numerous failed operations that were only fixed or made better through the intervention of tier 1 and tier 2 assets. However, the saving of Captain Phillips by the DEVGRU team (tier 1)²⁶, most illustrates the issue of preparation and execution, to complete the objective with 100% resolution^{27, 28}.

From an ORDA:INED²⁹, practical standpoint

The point of using the US Army's science of Operations Research³⁰ (invented in World War II) is to obviously make things run smoother. This is pretty important from an operator's perspective.

Data Analytics enables an evidence based decision making chain, by looking across the empirical evidence, and making the highest MAMA ratio decision; and creating a plan A, B, C, or even D.

But that isn't the end of the story. On the far end of the spectrum, as the author has defined it, we see crossover with several areas; and from there towards the SSIVA:PADEP paradigm as a whole.

Figure 4 - ORDAINED//PADEP; credit: author

²² [MIMS 2.83 - POS Theory](#)

²³ [MIMS & Shi](#)

²⁴ [Axioms of Power by Shifu Ramon](#)

²⁵ [Axioms of Influence, Affluence, and Access by Shifu Careaga](#)

²⁶ [Captian Philips Best Execute scene by SEAL TEAM - HD 720p](#)

²⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LPOhtTPv6oI>

²⁸ [The Real Maersk Alabama/Somali Pirate story \(Never seen before footage\)](#)

²⁹ [MESS0007: The ORDA Standard](#)

³⁰ [Operations Research: Introduction, Historical Background](#)

1. Actionability - corresponding to analytics, and therefore to Numericalization, means that we can **literally** “run things by the numbers.”
 - a. Borrows from the *N* power³¹, rather than (as usual), from the *P* power³², which is “drained out” from obsessive technocratic bureaucrats.
2. Intensity - as shown is going to be related to the implementation, why: because to implement a **Plan**, we need to **prepare** to execute it - perhaps whatever the costs
3. Experience is what relates us to this ability to plan, prepare, and execute the plan.
4. Devastation - becomes therefore, and finally, improved via increased, and increasing definition: “honing in” on our plans.
 - a. Pre-engineering, pre-search, and preparation are nothing³³, unless we really work through the issues, and define our situational needs (through situational awareness), to come to executable conclusions.
 - b. Indecision and indecisiveness, come from a distortion of the Field, which results in a lack of coherence, and synchronicity³⁴ with the moment.

Actionability

Action Ability means literally one’s own capabilities *in a firefight*, or a hand-to-hand, or a technological action picture.

Willing, Capable, and Able; Not ENOUGH!

Normally, in self-defense and martiality, the main issue with dealing with Nature Awareness (predator-prey dynamics) is a matter of willingness, capability, and ability. The subtle difference between the two latter, is that capability is potential, and ability is the physical actual means to activate that capability. Willingness is often the central axis to that, and it might be a matter of wisdom, or it might be a matter of *force of personality*. This is usually called gravitas, or ‘personal magnetism’ or ‘animal magnetism’ - the “it” or “X-factor” - whatever it is, it’s not numerically valued.

However, this is not enough to guarantee success in operations. But, the L.U.C.K.³⁵ and “soldier of fortune” situation, which creates a sense of invisible protection over certain guys, isn’t trainable. It’s something the operator has to read about, and want. They have to want to be like this guy:

Figure 5 (gif) - “Good morning Sergeant Major,” credit: “We Were Soldiers”/Iconic Productions³⁶

³¹ [MIMS - The Big G of 5 Forces](#)

³² [MESS0047: Investigation of MIMS Matrices of Reality with a Realonic Philosphaether Approach](#)

³³ Just as American Integrated Circuits turned out to be:

[MESS0026: MIMS 3.11 - AIC as a Pre-Engineering AIM+ and SPACERS-Resilient compliant Project](#) is retracted!

³⁴ [Synchronicity - an overview | ScienceDirect Topics](#)

³⁵ [Were Soldiers Nice Day Sgt Savage Complete](#)

³⁶ If you don’t know/get this reference, it isn’t for you, and you will never be that guy.

Devastation

To understand the concept of increasing devastation through ***Intense Violence of Action***, then we must look into the concepts of devastating penetration and potency. The following image action gifs, demonstrate the concept well:

Figure 6 ([gif](#)) - Rail gun testing

Figure 7 - Railgun vs. 2" steel plate penetration, at USN testing³⁷

³⁷ [Six 2" steel plates penetrated by a slug from a railgun during USN testing \[1200x671\]](#)

And to understand Devastation, we simply need to watch how the SEALs' SWCC operate.

Figure 8 ([gif](#)) - Speed, Surprise, and Intensely Violent Action; credit: "Act of Valor"/Relativity Media

Experience - all things being equal, wisdom wins

The header says it all; but a couple of points or anecdotes to illustrate the issue. The author has seen this situation rule in favor of the wise - who consider the prudent timing of things - in both nature and human affairs. He has seen old bull giraffes beat young, big bulls. He has seen old boxing coaches absolutely destroy young men in their prime in the ring. He has seen old players hit 'impossible' shot after shot, by going slow and methodically.

Now, imagine that these situations are actually between two [basically] equal forces. Which would you bank your money or place your bet on? That bet, is your life, freedom, and country. So, all things being equal, bet on Experience - bet on wisdom.

L.U.C.K. as a data field of actionable intelligence

Living Under Correct Knowledge is important, generally, in life because - all things being equal - it keeps on safe, and coming home at night to wife and kids, etc. At the end of the day, people want to come home to a place they belong. So the idea among the gamer community who play simulators, of "no HUD" and "less weapons" etc. is nonsense. Operators carry as many tools as they can that will help them get out safely. They're often limited by their kit, or what they can afford, but that doesn't mean they wouldn't take something "off the shelf" or homemade. If they had a HUD that told them where an enemy was, they'd use it!

Now the Common Operating Picture of the HUD is based on a data field of actionable intel. Below is an actual example of the "HUD" inside a new Abrams X tank:

Figure 9 ([gif](#)) - "Abrams X HUD"; credit: Task & Purpose [▶ America's New Abrams-X Tank Needs to Chill Out](#)
★ Remember: the map is not the terrain; the more you [correctly] know, the better.

Potency - You have to penetrate the Enemy's defenses and capabilities, and control the War Field Codes of Control (WFCC)

Read: [MESS0037: MIMS 2.801 - the Eight Domain Array](#)

Kinetic Penetration

Figure 10 ([gif](#)) - Bullet into armor penetration

Aside from the above view, let's also think about the danger of a lack of kinetic or ballistic penetration.

It is 'not good' if your attempts to penetrate a situation are made impotent because there is a serious lack of the penetrative effect of your Shi. If it is a literal kinetic object, this is problematic.

Also, if there is no object but it is sound, words, or particles, you have to make sure you're reaching through to the target - the 'load -' so that the **penetration goes past the adversary's defense layers.**

The author has a saying: "I never count my chickens until their heads are cut off. Because there are always foxes." He also has a saying/meme:

Figure 11 - "Hit them in the Paradigium" (a fictional organ³⁸); credit: author

- ★ Meaning: if you're going to strike, strike with such a force as to change their entire outlook on life and on you, as a potential prey or victim to abuse.

³⁸ And double reference to a basketball movie.

Dynamic Penetration

Rocky Marciano - 49-0 - Hardest Hitter In Boxing History (A Knockout Documentary)

Figure 12 - Rocky Marciano delivers a “jin” ‘thunderpunch’ of a cross, and liquifies this man’s face;
credit: BoredFilm/Joseph Vincent³⁹

In terms of pound for pound devastation, it doesn’t get much more ‘make the bar go to 100’ than the above photograph, which is not an artifact (damn! Look at that guy’s eyeball)

But when we want to talk about dynamic penetration we simply must talk about Jin 勁 - vibration - and the effect it has on the whole execution/’job done’ thing. It has the effect of being absolutely brutal in terms of delivery (as you see above), but also of rattling their cage. It gets passed defensive layers into the ‘heart’ of the adversary, and whether it is literal shellshock or just hitting them in the ‘paradigm’, the net result is devastation=100. This has a demoralization effect that is of inestimable value in ending conflict with fewer casualties.

Figure 13 (gif) - Batman with the hard hitting interrogation methods;
credit: DC/WB

³⁹ [Rocky Marciano - 49-0 - Hardest Hitter In Boxing History \(A Knockout Documentary\)](#)

Organic Penetration

In terms of slowly penetrating, you have the facet of vine-like growth, which can be combined with parasitic or poisonous penetration (say: in terms of cartels or terrorist cells, etc.; ie- espionage). The classic film story retold over and over again “Yojimbo”⁴⁰ demonstrates the effect of slowly, but with better maneuvering, penetrating the adversaries’ defenses.

Deft Penetration

Whereas deft penetration is generally the involvement of skilled operation (of a spy or asset) into an organization or situation, in order to maneuver a stratagem into place. Usually, it is, a ‘divide and conquer’ but it could be for any number of reasons. The resultant of this behavior is to be able to “plant the plastique” in a ‘shatterpoint’⁴¹ or ‘nexus point’ in the adversary’s infrastructure, armor, or morale; and to detonate it. Often one can get away ‘scott free’ and keep the operation ‘black’. If the enemy has no Force/Field detection - no ‘eyes on’ - it will be difficult for them to detect and prevent.

Figure 14 ([gif](#)) - realistic armor penetration simulation⁴²

Viral Penetration

Heading deeper into the ‘yin’ field, towards more deception or dark methods (black ops) we find that there is a type of penetration that is both complete, and can lay a program of deterioration, and also can spread of its own accord. The most common form of this is propaganda, then there is disinformation and misinformation campaigns, and of course certain types of psyops. This is the specialty of the CIA, and of the Green Berets⁴³ (Special Forces) which are infiltrating an area. However, there is one specific Tom Clancy’s

⁴⁰ [YouTube](#) YOJIMBO Trailer (1961) - The Criterion Collection

⁴¹ <https://www.amazon.com/Shatterpoint-Star-Wars-Clone/dp/0345455746/>

⁴² [Forget about realistic armour penetration - Page 3](#)

⁴³ <https://www.amazon.com/Special-Forces-Clancys-Military-Referenc/dp/0425172686/>

book about this, “Under Fire,” which deals with methods of creating subversive overthrow via “Unrestricted Warfare”⁴⁴ techniques. And the goal is to spread a message far, fast, and *deep*, before the adversary has time enough to react to it.

Parasitic Penetration

In the act of committing espionage, subversion, or black ops, there is an opportunity for the operator or spy to also place a leeching program onto the host organism. For example, if there is a sabotage of a power grid planned, there is also the ability to install backpacks into the substation software, and make sure it has firmly wormed its way into the system before destroying the evidence that anyone was there. If an SF team is overthrowing a genocidal dictator, then there is every reason to also place spying devices around the palaces, fortifications, infrastructure, etc. to learn of their entire network, hitherto operating underground or sans cellular, in order to figure out ‘who will take over this monstrous organization after we knock off the top monster?’ In eliminating hydras, it is not enough to cut off one or two heads. You have to stab the monster through the heart. Without that direct action capability, you can parasitically penetrate the organizational structure, and then eliminate it down to root and tip, and rip the seed out of the earth, so to speak.

Operating as a Violent Act of Love and Hope

It’s a difficult sale to make, that violence can be loving or hoping. But in fact gongfu teachers have been using this premise for thousands and thousands of years. By using distributed, non-permanent, non-personal damage, you can strengthen the body, mind, and spirit of the ones you love or care for, or have custodianship over.

It is important for the distributor of this ‘controlled abuse’ such as it is, not really being abuse but growth instigation:

1. Not be neglectful or create resentment.
2. Not be purposefully highly-violent to the trainee (especially if it is a child or one’s own child)
3. Not be permanently debilitating in any form.
 - a. This last one is important because the tendency in martial arts studios, especially in America⁴⁵ but historically, too, has been to overinflict damage⁴⁶.

Creating Resiliency Through Early Exposure to Intense “Violence of Action”

There is an ability to help the soldier or operative by exposing them to IVA, much as is done in bootcamps⁴⁷. The point of creating this resiliency is not merely toughness. It’s to increase competency. Competency can come from training, practice, and repetition; it can also be induced via an arms’ race (so to speak). As two sides intensely battle, there is an early stage where resiliency is increased; long term though it collapses.

⁴⁴ [Unrestricted Warfare](#)

⁴⁵ [How to Spot a Toxic Martial Arts Club Environment - Breaking Muscle](#)

⁴⁶ One famous historical example is “Yin Fu” who wore a large mustache for the rest of his life, because when he was 16 he mouthed off to the sifu. While mouthing off Sifu performed “Snake Penetrates the Soul” and it knocked out his two front teeth. He was so embarrassed that for the rest of his life he hid the shame of it away. While this did effectively give a lesson on ego, it’s probably going way too far. Times also have changed, and this would be a lawsuit situation.

⁴⁷ [YouTube US Marines Train in the Most Realistic Live-Fire Range There is](#)

The anti-MIMS of militarism, and why some militias become hate-groups

Militarism, however, while it initially seems to provide ever growing strength, leads inevitably to the antithesis of gathering strength: expulsiveness. Being expulsive, the gathered AME⁴⁸ and spiritual mass of charged ambition and naked aggression rushes forward from a source towards almost any vulnerable nearby node. Hence Germany invading Poland. There wasn't any good reason, it's just the 'path of least resistance' (literally), and the currency flowed in that direction. But the explosiveness of the event, and the sudden rush, is problematic for the source and load together. This is because of the nature of energy, and electrical laws, so that the MAMA is strengthened in its source-load connection, and the MAMA swaps rapidly from highly mimsical to highly anti-mimsical as what was proper development becomes outright destruction. There are the results of the flow of Raw and Destructive Power⁴⁹, from source to load, and backwashing back to the source. The MAMA enables the Devastation bar, so to speak, to revert back upon the one with all the power!

It is therefore another cause for concern regarding the formation of militias. Militias are good; great really. We need thousands of them, and well armed, of all races and proclivities. But what we don't need are ones that gather such an arsenal they start imagining they can and should overthrow the local government, or can and should go after specific races. These are the results of the vectors of gathered energies of Raw Potential, which can be converted by anti-mimsical philosophies and personalities into directed Destructive Power. So in the establishment of Westmooreland's 'paintball teams,'⁵⁰ let the organizer not be too hasty in making such a good team he expands beyond the invisible shell of the team's natural niche/boundaries and into this area of devastation.

Building healthy militias in the West as unique cultural and national defenses that do not threaten a viable Republic and general ideas of democracy; but protect from their weaknesses and abuses.

The title is purposefully long, for the table of contents to reflect that this is a great and important value. How can we do this, and what does it have to do with operators? We should, in fact, set up militias with operators at the core, in the following three ways:

1. Operator only, 'core' teams - very small.
2. Operator led, veteran and police/EMF only teams - medium to small, except as needed then medium-large is acceptable.
3. Operator led training groups for common citizens and survivalists - small to very small.

The weaknesses and abuses come from egos that have the following characteristics:

1. Narcissistic
2. Dark Empathic
3. Highly Manipulative
4. Sociopathic
5. Psychopathic
6. Neurotic or Personality Disordered

⁴⁸ Atomic mass energy

⁴⁹ Secret Axioms of Secret Power

⁵⁰ Central KY Airsoft

This is not to single out highly effective and ambitious people. However, there is a direct need to deal with the manipulative ways of the above personalities, when you start adding firearms, capabilities, and other weapons into the mix.

The FBI may be worthless these days⁵¹, but assuming they or BATF, or the Marshalls would be interested in preventing 'homegrown' terrorism, organized crime, and radical extremist elements, they should cease to inflame all militias by lumping them together, and focus on the rights aspect (Constitutional protection) and also the common sense aspect. If a type 2 militia is acquiring full auto, that's not really a big deal; they are used to those weapons. If a type 2 is suddenly acquiring fertilizer that's concerning enough to investigate them. If a type 3 is acquiring suppressors, this is not a problem per se. However if a type 1 is suddenly buying suppressors and body armor, suspect a terrorism event. Etc.

All the citizens above have rights, but inevitably when you search through their membership rolls, what types will you find in the extremist (usually leftist, alt-right, or racial supremacists) organizations? Criminals, with backgrounds. When Kyle Rittenhouse rid the world of two and a half POS, the FBI and others came after him. But it turned out all three [white] men were criminals, rapists, and one was a pedophile.⁵² He did the world a favor, and this is what a type 3 organization involving common people should be able to do, in a defensive posture (such as he was, with the riots and burning down of family property⁵³).

And if someone politically (not religiously) disagrees with this, undoubtedly they are a POS simp⁵⁴ and part of the unethical overthrow of society.

Special Forces Used at Home in Peaceable Actions and not Covert PsyOps

What happened in the 2020 elections... with the mules breaking mail-in ballot laws for \$10 a ballot⁵⁵, and the hate groups attacking and instigating patriots⁵⁶ with the help of the FBI⁵⁷, and the subsequent 'cattleprodding' of people who weren't super savvy or smart⁵⁸, but hopped up on righteous and patriotic anger⁵⁹... proves that operators can and should have a helpful impact at home. Through leadership, and *unofficial*, but effective crowd control and guidance. It's true that right now operators are mostly taught violence, but over time the SF 'soft tactics' of the Green Beret mission will spread over time, and men of extraordinary means and skills will be able to stand up missions of peace and spread mimsical leadership. They can do so by:

- Infiltrate local extremist organizations and
 - Turn low hanging fruit back to the Light.
 - Gather HUMINT⁶⁰ on misguided patriots looking to hurt innocents.
 - Direct espionage of the leaders of these homegrown terror cells.
- Keep rioters' tempers lowered and
 - Identify and remove agitators, by force if necessary.

⁵¹ [MESS0045: POS vs. The Deep State](#)

⁵² [Man Fatally Shot By Rittenhouse Was A Sex Offender: Attorney | Libertyville, IL Patch](#)

⁵³ [Kyle Rittenhouse And Every Able-Bodied Man Had A Moral Obligation To Protect Kenosha](#)

⁵⁴ [MESS0006: POS Theory Grows Because Agenda](#)

⁵⁵ [2,000 Mules: They Thought We'd Never Find Out. They Were Wrong.: D'Souza, Dinesh: 9781684514465](#)

⁵⁶ [Two known Antifa members posed as pro-Trump to infiltrate Capitol riot: sources](#)

⁵⁷ [FBI had informant in crowd during Capitol riot: report | The Hill](#)

⁵⁸ [Their loved ones are 'obsessed' with QAnon conspiracies. It's tearing their families apart](#)

⁵⁹ [Day of Rage: How Trump Supporters Took the U.S. Capitol | Visual Investigations](#)

⁶⁰ Human Intelligence

- Feds or terrorists, either present a Clear and Present Danger⁶¹.
 - Lead through voice and deed.
 - Provide soft security.
 - Use a show of force or intimidation to keep heightened 'nutballs' from going to a level of 'no return'
 - Provide hard security from mass shooters (with ruthless efficiency)
 - Behave as confident 'coolers'⁶² and do not always dress up in tac or look menacing or even like an operator
- Thwarting government control over First Amendment actions:
 - Speech
 - Religion
 - Press
 - Expression that is not violating SCOTUS rulings
- Protecting polling places, infrastructure, schools, hospitals, and grocery stores
 - Most probably do this on their own
 - Need to conceal carry **at all times**.
 - See: mass shooter threat⁶³

The problem with using operators as the FBI has with (eg. Gov. Whitmer entrapment situation) its own resources, is that you're unable to prove that you're on the mimsical end of covert action. And that is so key for staying both legal and ethical, and of course creating moral, wise, healthy outcomes that respect others' rights and the country at large.

And isn't that what is key about our social contract in this Republic For Which It Stands? People want to protest? Fine. Be loud, even be annoying, so long as you're not violating night ordinances, and creating an unsafe environment. But you have no right, left, right or center, domestic or foreign, to present a Clear and Present Danger to others/the public.

And that goes **double** for the government. If you're FBI and reading this, you need to understand the POS history of your organization, and your training is ineptly provided (clearly) to respect the public's rights. But that isn't the end of the story. Consider this poem, written by chatGPT/weaponoutfitters (figure 15):

⁶¹ [Clear and Present Danger Test | The First Amendment Encyclopedia](#)

⁶² [The Right Training For Bouncers, Doormen and Coolers](#)

⁶³ [Firearms Facts Graphs.pdf](#)

So let's all take a moment to reflect, "what is our social contract and responsibilities?" If you're an operator, you now have a theoretically enhanced knowledge set to increase your SSIVA:PADEP through the SSIVA:PADEP concept, and retain all your ability to be on the low or high end of the MAMA scale. But, do you have the ethical fortification, and the moral brass and boundaries⁶⁴, to do so?

Figure 16 - "Lord"⁶⁵ Shiva, God of Destruction (and overloaded with symbols of weaponry and electrical thunderbolts) - probably not a surprise that this is so similar to SSIVA! Credit: "Smite"/GameSpot⁶⁶
Clip-art added by the author (as a joke)

ॐ Namah SSIVA

⁶⁴ [Boundaries: When to Say Yes, How to Say No to Take Control of Your Life](#)

⁶⁵ The author is a Christaoist, this is a meme.

⁶⁶ [Smite Adds Hindu Deity Shiva To Its Godly Roster - GameSpot](#)

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